

MILK PRODUCTIVITY OF SHVITZKIY COWS OF AUSTRIAN SELECTION

Mavlonov S.I.¹, Bahridinov F.B.², Khidirov K.I.³

¹ Candidate of Veterinary Sciences, head of department of the State Administration of Veterinary Medicine and Livestock Development,

² PhD, DSc doctoral student at Fergana State University,

³ Director of rabbit breeding and genetic center

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6300478>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th February 2022

Accepted: 15th February 2022

Online: 25th February 2022

KEY WORDS

breed, selection, cows, productivity, milk, milk fat, feed units, fodder payment, lactation.

ABSTRACT

The results of researches have shown the good adaptability of cows of Austrian selection to conditions of the Republic, high milk productivity and the better fodder self-payment.

Introduction. Today, cattle breeding occupies a special place in meeting the increasing food needs of the world's population. In this connection "in such countries with developed cattle breeding as the USA, Germany, Holland, Canada, Japan, Israel and European Union much attention is given to improvement of productive, reproductive, technological qualities of cattle, wide use of genetic potential of bulls-producers at artificial insemination, providing with valuable feeding, improvement of selection-tribal work and conditions of keeping, breeding of highly productive breeds of animals. As a result of carried out work increase of number of highly productive dairy herds, growth of milk productivity level of cows and improvement of their adaptability to modern milking installations Shvitskaya breed of cattle, zoned for breeding in farms of our republic, being one of leading breeds of combined direction, by number takes the

third place and by milk productivity the second place among other breeds.

Cows of Schwyzka breed differ by high fat content in milk, duration of use in a farm, proportionate developed exterior, good adaptive qualities in conditions of foothill zones and various climatic conditions. In addition, the young stock of the breed is characterized by high growth energy, good payment for feed production. In improving the productive properties of the breed and improving the basic breeding properties, in reproduction towards artificial insemination, semen of Shvitzky bulls-producers of the world gene pool of Swiss, German, Austrian, Russian, American selections are widely used. The use of bulls of Swiss breed of the world gene pool in mating expands the possibilities of genetic improvement of productive qualities of the breed and creation of highly productive herds that has an important scientific and practical meaning and is actual.

Material and research methodology. The Scientific study was conducted in farming facilities "Samo Chashmasi" Sh. Rashidov region Dzhizak area itself.

Two groups of Shvitzkiy cows of III and older lactation with 15 cows in each group were selected for the experiment. The Nursing of both groups cortex was sister.

Cows of the local selection have been selected in group I, in group II - cows of the

Austrian breed, imported from Europe. Feeding in - all groups was the same.

Group I consumed 4595,0 fodder units and 538,5 kg of digestible protein per cow and Group II consumed 4670,4 and 542,2 kg per lactation, respectively.

Research results. The main indicator in assessing the breeding value of cows of different breeding is milk productivity. Table 1 shows the data of milk productivity of cows for lactation in the experimental groups.

Table 1

Indicators of milk productivity of cows

Indicators	Groups			
	I (n-15)		II (n-15)	
	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	C _v ,%	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	C _v ,%
Milk yield, kg	4177,3±85,4	7,62	4364,9±103,6	8,88
Milk fat, %	4,13±0,03	3,72	4,07±0,04	3,43
Milk fat yield, kg	172,5±2,57	5,40	177,6±2,77	5,85
Milk yield 4%, kg	4313,1±59,7	5,22	4441,3±71,3	5,98
Milk yield coefficient, kg	816,0±15,6	3,46	844±15,1	6,80
Live weight, kg	511,9±4,73	3,46	525,8±6,84	4,34
Dry matter,%	12,68		12,61	
CATFISH,%	8,71		8,69	
Protein content in milk,%	3,68		3,64	
Sugar content in milk,%	4,53		4,52	

As it can be seen from the data of table 1, the milk yield of cows in group II during lactation was 187,6 kg (P>0,999), the milk fat yield was 5,1 kg (P>0,999), the milk yield was 138,2 kg (P>0,999) higher than that of cows in group I and the milk yield was 24,1 kg (P>0,99) respectively.

It should be noted that the content of dry matter, DMSO (dry skimmed milk residue), protein and sugar content in the milk of cows in all the experimental groups was at a good level.

Consequently, the milk yield of Schwyzka cows of Austrian breeding showed a high level.

As can be seen from Table 2, the cows of experimental group II had a higher level of forage payment for dairy products in comparison with the cows of experimental group I. Thus, in group II the cows spent respectively 4,5 % less fodder units to produce 1 kg of natural fat milk and 1,1 % of 4% milk, but produced 2,55 kg (2,8 %) of natural and 1,23 kg (1,3 %) of 4% milk per

every 100 kg of fodder units more than the cows of group I.

Table 2

Indicators of fodder payment for milk production of cows

Indicators	Groups	
	I (n-15)	II (n-15)
Feed unit spent per cow per lactation, kg	4595,0	4670,4
Milk yield, kg	4177,3	4364,9
Milk yield 4%, kg	4313,1	4441,3
Fodder unit costs for production 1 kg of natural milk, kg	1,10	1,05
The cost of feed units for the production of 1 kg of 4% milk, kg	1,06	1,05
For every 100 fodder units produced natural milk, kg	90,91	93,46
4% milk, kg	93,86	95,09

Conclusions. In all experimental groups, regardless of origin, milk productivity was high and uniform lactation was observed. Cows of Austrian selection had high daily milk yields in all

periods of lactation and the best quality indicators of milk, that testifies to adaptability to the conditions of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES:

1. Ashirov M.I. Perfection of Shvitz cattle in Uzbekistan. Tashkent, "Navruz" publishing house, 2020, p.192.
2. Ashirov M., Soatov Y., Ashirov B., Nasirdinov Yo. Turli genotipdagi shvits zotli sigirlarning sut maxsuldorligi. Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiya materiallari tuplami. Toshkent, 2011, 6-8 b.130.9
3. Lyashuk R.N., Shendakov A.I., Vostroilov M.V., et al. Increasing the genetic potential of dairy cattle. Moscow, 2007, №11, pp.3-5.
4. Lapina N.N., Kovaleva G.P., Vitol V.A., Kovaleva T.P. Genetic factors influencing the reproductive qualities of dairy cows. Zootehnia, №7, 2008, pp. 4-5
5. Prakhov L.P., Koval L.L., Vorobyova N.V. Exterior features of highly productive cows. Zootehnia. Moscow, 2010, No. 7, pp. 12-14.